

THE IMPORTANCE OF WOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract: *In this scientific article, attempts were made to study the socio-philosophical aspects of the scientific and theoretical formation of a combination of family and entrepreneurial women's relations in the era of globalization and modernization carried out in our society, its social dynamics, as well as its role in the social, economic and cultural development of our republic. In the new era of our development, the problem of family and women's entrepreneurship attracts attention not only of national, but also of universal importance.*

Keywords: *entrepreneurship, family business, gender relations, entrepreneurial woman, integration, globalization, modernization, social sphere, socialization, philosophical analysis, social dynamics.*

ОИЛАВИЙ ТАДБИРКОРЛИКНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ХОТИН-ҚИЗЛАРНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ

Аннотация: *Ушбу илмий мақолада жамиятимизда амалга оширилаётган глобаллашув ва модернизация даврида оилавий ва тадбиркор аёл муносабатларининг уйғунлашуви илмий-назарий жиҳатдан шаклланиши, унинг ижтимоий динамикаси, шунингдек республикамизнинг ижтимоий, иқтисодий ҳамда маданий ривожланишидаги ўрни ижтимоий-фалсафий жиҳатларини тадқиқ қилишга ҳаракат қилинган. Тараққиётимизнинг янги даврида оилавий ва аёл тадбиркорлиги масаласи нафақат миллий, балки умумбашарий аҳамиятга эга эканлиги ҳам эътиброга моликдир.*

Калит сўзлар: *тадбиркорлик, оилавий бизнес, гендер муносабатлари, тадбиркор аёл, интеграция, глобаллашув, модернизация, ижтимоий соҳа, ижтимоилашув, фалсафий таҳлил, социал динамика.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ ЖЕНЩИН В РАЗВИТИИ СЕМЕЙНОГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА

Аннотация: *В данной научной статье были предприняты попытки изучить социально-философские аспекты научно-теоретического формирования сочетания семейных и предпринимательских женских отношений в эпоху глобализации и модернизации, осуществляемой в нашем обществе, его социальную динамику, а также роль в социальном, экономическом и культурном развитии нашей республики. В новую эпоху нашего развития проблема семьи и женского предпринимательства привлекает внимание не только национального, но и общечеловеческого значения.*

Ключевые слова: *предпринимательство, семейный бизнес, гендерные отношения, предпринимательская женщина, интеграция, глобализация, модернизация, социальная сфера, социализация, философский анализ, социальная динамика.*

INTRODUCTION

During the activities of an entrepreneur, it is important to rely on national-cultural values, value secular values, not to forget about the factors, reasons that gave rise to entrepreneurial activity, and to be like-minded among business entities. Harmony in the interaction of entrepreneurs is reflected in the attitude of the object to the subject, in the course of interpersonal relations, as well as in the attitude of the individual to information communicative processes. This

process also has its influence on the system of socio-economic relations. In the process of studying social relations, an entrepreneur acquires scientifically based information about real practice, directly related to his activities, gives an objective assessment of his entrepreneurial activity, his place in society, and collects information of intellectual content necessary to effectively ensure entrepreneurship in this process. It is recognized that the intellectual potential of the entrepreneur helps to summarize the socio-cultural and social-philosophical aspects of his actions in this area. Also, the creative analysis of the activities of an entrepreneur is manifested in the development of new technological functions necessary for the activities of an entrepreneur, rules of order of social content.

It should be noted that business entities regularly strive for a quality, product that meets the requirements of the market, produced as a result of their activities. An important role in this is played by the creative approach of the entrepreneur to his activities, that is, the fact that he was able to find his place in the economic indicators of business relations from a professional point of view, in the systems of society, in the solution of social problems.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

In the development of family business, the features inherent in our national mentality, its certain facets, the Uzbek nation, it is the traditions in the development of women's Activities, National values that are reflected to some extent. As a result of the liberal democratic reforms carried out during the years of independence, conditions were created for the expansion of family business entities. Its legal, organizational, financial foundations are being improved. At the new stage of development, there are facilities for all its forms in order to ensure the stability of the family and women's business and in order to strengthen its position in the development of society.

The role of private property in the development and development of family and women's business plays an important role. Special attention was paid to the place of private property in the development of society, and the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan established its protection by the state: "private property, like other forms of property, is dahlless and under the protection of the state. The owner can be deprived of his property only in cases and procedures provided for by law"[1]. In this regard, it should be noted that in the activities of entrepreneurs engaged in family business in Uzbekistan at the present time, following national traditions, special attention is paid to traditional human resources, crafts, livestock and agriculture, which have been formed in the regions of our country for centuries and passed down from generation to generation. Representatives of the family and women's business play an important role in the formation of the farming movement and peasant farms formed during the years of independence, their transformation into important business entities in society. In this process, an attempt is being made by family entrepreneurs to introduce new technologies, innovations in order to improve the types of entrepreneurship, the above forms of which are mentioned.

As a result of the occupation and crafts, the types of goods offered to the market were expanded, in this process, a series of goods was created, designed for export to foreign countries and for the tourism industry, which is rapidly developing in our country. It should be noted that one of the new joints, which is gaining significant practical importance in the development of Uzbekistan, is the tourism industry. The result of scientific research shows that at the next time, as a result of the efforts of representatives of the family business in our country, the hotel business, the restaurant type of Service are being organized and developed at a pace corresponding to our development. As a result, the number of travelers who visited the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019 amounted to 7 million. made up the man. It should be noted that the increase in the flow of tourists

in our country indicates an increase in the number and quality of the types of services offered to them. Also, the participation of the family business in the development of tourism has arisen a type of pilgrimage, which is its new forms, which plays an important role in the service sector. In this process, the activities of translators, guides were improved to serve foreign tourists. A map of the historical monuments existing in our country, that is, information booklets with a geographical location, literature in English, Russian, Chinese, French, German, was published: "in the current period, there are 8,208 monuments of material culture in our country in total, of which 4,748 are memorials on archeology, 2,250 are monuments of historical importance, 678 are monumental.

In order to train highly qualified personnel necessary for the further development of tourism in Uzbekistan, Samarkand state tourism university was established. The main goal of these complex activities is to improve the basis of the socio-economic direction favorable for all types of entrepreneurial activity, to improve the quality of family entrepreneurship, which is an important link in its development. As a result of comprehensive measures in this area, economic and organizational support for family entrepreneurship, the role of this link in the reform process is strengthened, all conditions are created for the organization of family business at the level of international requirements.

In order to raise the activities of entrepreneurs and ensure their competitiveness in our country, retraining, professional development courses were organized designed for them. In this process, the qualifications of entrepreneurs are being developed, using the capabilities of information and communication technologies at a distance. All conditions have been created for entrepreneurs to get acquainted with the experience of the business system in developed countries.

Currently, it is important for entrepreneurs to become representatives of competitive entrepreneurship due to the awareness of knowledge related to their field, a set of ideas and the ability to establish themselves as active actors operating not only in the country, but also in the international arena. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev noted: "At the same time, not everyone can become an entrepreneur. Therefore, systematically working with such people and retraining them in the profession, it is necessary to provide them with a suitable place of work"[3].

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the results of our scientific research, it became clear that family business and small business are among the main factors contributing to the strategic development of the country. Especially in connection with the importance of this process, the beginning of the entrepreneurial movement of innovative content in society, its wide development is increasing. At present, the strategic development stage of the family business is characterized by the following factors:

- pay attention to human interests and needs; achieve high efficiency in the activities of business representatives;
- independent thinking, which is necessary for the development of family business; not to be afraid of an action that acquires novatorial significance;
- to withstand the shortcomings, failures encountered in entrepreneurial activity; to pay attention to the activities of participants, members of the entrepreneur's family business;
- when doing business, it is required to think independently, act, in turn, not to forget about personal responsibility.

In a dynamically developing society, it has become a necessity for a person who creatively approaches entrepreneurial activity, thinks intellectually and tries to achieve only positive results. The degree of competence of an entrepreneur is influenced by his computer literacy, high mastery

of computer technology necessary for entrepreneurship, knowledge of one of the foreign languages.

These requirements increasingly require a growing presence in society of leading innovators who are trying to apply them to their activities, innovations – innovative individuals corresponding to an active social phenomenon. Because the rise of democratic processes in society and the economic sphere increases the demand for a person with innovative consciousness, innovative thinking. “A new social transformation appears in society: instead of unconditional executors of all assignments, people are required who can quickly find their way in different situations, creatively solve the problems that have arisen, make an understandable decision, take on his personal responsibility, have a creative and flexible mind, have the opportunity to make a choice that characterizes the novelty, actively participate in social reforms”[4].

This process is the basis for solving problems with the virtual opportunities necessary for the activities of the entrepreneur and at an accelerated pace. In particular, through the internet system, there will be an opportunity to sign trade agreements, approve contracts, conduct financial relations, study the most advanced experience in the country and abroad, establish the necessary electronic commerce in determining the future of entrepreneurial activity.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, at present, more than 10 million people use computer technology in our country, especially since this process plays an important role in the activities of business entities. Especially among family businesses, small businesses, the effective use of computers is increasing at a regular pace. In the process of improving society, all opportunities were created for the movement of our country to have an independent information system, as well as for independent information dissemination, a personnel Corps was created, potential journalists began to work. In order to further improve the productive work in this direction and to regularly cover young people, representatives of the population, the content, purpose, development trends of family business and entrepreneurship, the shortcomings encountered in this area, a new generation of the media began to work. In particular, the newspaper” New Uzbekistan "in the internet system “Kun.uz" we can cite information Editing, channels on Uzbek television “Uzbekistan”, “history of Uzbekistan” and other media. The state of the family business, the process of productive work that is being achieved in it, we can see in the activities of all newspapers and magazines working in our country, the articles published on their pages play an important factor in increasing the interest of young people in family business.

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